

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIALS

Modeling Electric Scooter Adoption in Data-Scarce Midsize Cities: An Agent Based Simulation for Oakville, Ontario

Tyler Yutai Hu,¹ Sk. Md. Mashrur, Ph.D.,² Saeed Shakib, Ph.D.,³ Eric Chan, P.Eng.,⁴ and Khandker Nurul
Habib, Ph.D., P.Eng.⁵

¹M.A.Sc. Student, Department of Civil & Mineral Engineering, University of Toronto, 35 St. George
Street, Toronto, Canada, M5S 1A4; email: tyler.hu@mail.utoronto.ca (Corresponding author)

²Postdoctoral Fellow, Department of Civil & Mineral Engineering, University of Toronto, 35 St. George
Street, Toronto, Canada, M5S 1A4; email: sm.mashrur@mail.utoronto.ca

³Postdoctoral Fellow, Department of Civil & Mineral Engineering, University of Toronto, 35 St. George
Street, Toronto, Canada, M5S 1A4; email: saeed.shakib@mail.utoronto.ca

⁴Manager of Transportation Planning, Town of Oakville, 1225 Trafalgar Road, Oakville, Canada, L6H 0H3

⁵Professor, Department of Civil & Mineral Engineering, University of Toronto, 35 St. George Street,
Toronto, Canada, M5S 1A4; email: khandker.nurulhabib@utoronto.ca

Table S1. Summary and classification of socio-demographic, spatial, and network attributes positively correlated with latent e-scooter demand, based on recent literature.

Type	Variables Affecting ES Demand	References
Socio-demographic attributes	Higher education background	(Badia and Jenelius 2023; Bai and Jiao 2020; Caspi et al. 2020; Christoforou et al. 2021; Laa and Leth 2020)
	Young age	(Abouelela et al. 2023; Badia and Jenelius 2023; Bai and Jiao 2020; Christoforou et al. 2021; Hosseinzadeh et al. 2021; Huang et al. 2024; Huo et al. 2021; Javadiansr et al. 2023; Mitra and Hess 2021; Yan et al. 2023; Yang et al. 2021)
	Gender: male	(Badia and Jenelius 2023; Christoforou et al. 2021; Hosseinzadeh et al. 2021; Huang et al. 2024; Javadiansr et al. 2023; Laa and Leth 2020; Mitra and Hess 2021; Yan et al. 2023)
	Marital status: single	(Mitra and Hess 2021)
	Race: non-white	(Huang et al. 2024; Yan et al. 2023)
Network attributes	Public transit (e.g., transit stops, improved service frequency)	(Abouelela et al. 2023; Bai and Jiao 2020; Caspi et al. 2020; Hosseinzadeh et al. 2021; Huo et al. 2021; Javadiansr et al. 2023; Reck et al. 2021a; Zuniga-Garcia et al. 2022)
	Bicycle infrastructure	(Abouelela et al. 2023; Caspi et al. 2020; Javadiansr et al. 2023; Mitra and Hess 2021; Reck et al. 2021a)
	Walkability	(Hosseinzadeh et al. 2021; Mitra and Hess 2021)

Type	Variables Affecting ES Demand	References
	Intersection/Road network density	(Caspi et al. 2020; Hosseinzadeh et al. 2021; Huo et al. 2021; Javadiansr et al. 2023)
	Safety (low accident rates and crime rates)	(Huang et al. 2024; Javadiansr et al. 2023; Mitra and Hess 2021)
Trip-related attributes	Weekends/Holidays	(Abouelela et al. 2023; Badia and Jenelius 2023; Bai and Jiao 2020; Caspi et al. 2020; Javadiansr et al. 2023; Noland 2021)
	Shorter distance/time	(Javadiansr et al. 2023; Reck et al. 2021b; Tørset et al. 2023; Yang et al. 2021)
	No change in elevation	(Reck et al. 2021b)
	Steady weather conditions (no precipitation, extreme temperature, or wind)	(Abouelela et al. 2023; Javadiansr et al. 2023; Noland 2021; Tørset et al. 2023; Zuniga-Garcia et al. 2022)
Land use attributes	Commercial (high employment rate)	(Badia and Jenelius 2023; Bai and Jiao 2020; Caspi et al. 2020; Hosseinzadeh et al. 2021; Huo et al. 2021; Javadiansr et al. 2023; Li et al. 2022)
	Recreational, Open space (parks, green space)	(Badia and Jenelius 2023; Bai and Jiao 2020; Hosseinzadeh et al. 2021; Li et al. 2022)
	Education (university, college)	(Bai and Jiao 2020; Caspi et al. 2020; Hosseinzadeh et al. 2021; Javadiansr et al. 2023; Reck et al. 2021a; Zuniga-Garcia et al. 2022)

Type	Variables Affecting ES Demand	References
	Downtown/Central business districts (high density)	(Badia and Jenelius 2023; Bai and Jiao 2020; Caspi et al. 2020; Hosseinzadeh et al. 2021; Huo et al. 2021; Javadiansr et al. 2023; Reck et al. 2021a; Zuniga-Garcia et al. 2022)
	Diversity of the land use	(Bai and Jiao 2020; Hosseinzadeh et al. 2021; Huo et al. 2021)
	Industrial	(Bai and Jiao 2020; Javadiansr et al. 2023; Li et al. 2022)

Fig. S1. Spatial distribution of latent short-trip demand (<5 km) overlaid with existing cycling infrastructure and regional MATSim network links, highlighting target corridors for micromobility deployment.

Fig. S2. Spatial distribution of socio-demographic indicators supportive of e-scooter adoption—including student population (A), median age (B), employment density (C), and transit pass ownership (D)—across Oakville traffic analysis zones.

Fig. S3. Baseline land-use classification across Oakville, utilized to identify commercial, recreational, and industrial zones with high spatial alignment for utilitarian e-scooter trips.

Fig. S4. Simulated median travel times and trip distances by mode across varying e-scooter utilities in Scenario 2.

Fig. S5. Distribution of e-scooter travel time (left) and distance (right) under the high utility scenario in Scenario 2.

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